

Novel hybrid chitosan/calcium phosphates microgels for remineralization of demineralized enamel - a model study

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Abstract

Dental caries remains one of the most prevalent bacteria caused diseases affecting both adults and children. It is a dynamic process which progress depends on the interplay between demineralization, caused by the bacteria produced acids from the consumption of sugars, and remineralization that takes place due to the saliva protective qualities/functions. The acids start to dissolve calcium and phosphate from the enamel (demineralization) and at the initial stage, when the tooth damage is not significant, the opposite process – the calcium and phosphate deposition (remineralization) could arrest the caries development thus making the caries a preventable disease. Thus, the development of new materials for enhancing the remineralization process is one of the main approaches of the non-invasive dentistry and also one of the main challenges of the advanced dental materials science.

In the present study, hybrid chitosan/calcium phosphates microgels were developed for the first time and their potential and effectiveness as remineralizing agent, enhancing the nucleation and growth of calcium phosphates on a model demineralized enamel surface, was revealed. The hybrid microgels formation was guided by the chitosan macromolecules which acted as a template for the calcium phosphate deposition and resulted into the *in situ* formation of amorphous to poorly crystalline non stoichiometric hydroxyapatite. These newly developed hybrid materials have several advantages as remineralizing agents, including bio-adhesiveness, antimicrobial properties as well as continuous supply of calcium and phosphate ions to ensure the successful remineralization of the model initial caries lesions.

Thus, the study reveals a simple and easy to apply remineralization procedure based on the newly developed hybrid materials that could be effectively used for arresting and enhancement of the remineralization of early-stage caries development taking advantage of the night regime

of the oral cavity habits. This simple approach has been tested and proved to be effective for remineralization of initial enamel demineralization.

Keywords: chitosan, calcium phosphates, hybride materials, microgels, enamel remineralization, caries arresting.

1. Introduction

Dental caries is one of the major public health problems, and a highly prevalent disease among the global population. It is an irreversible infectious, chronic disease, which progresses as a dynamic, multifactorial process and affects the mineralized dental structures[1]. Clinically, the dental caries is characterized by progressive demineralization of the tooth[2]. The demineralization is a result of the imbalance between the dissolution of calcium phosphates from the mineral part of the enamel and the remineralization. The dissolution rate exceeds the rate of the remineralization due to the unbalance in ionic concentration gradient between saliva and the area of enamel lesion and could finally result into an irreversible cavitation[1,3].

Although the dental caries is a preventable infectious disease, its prevention could fail due to many factors. The caries prevention is limited to the case when caries progression is related to de/remineralization in the early lesions, incipient caries and white spot. The advanced cavitation is the final stage for the caries prevention[2,4,5,6].

After the caries is formed, it could be cured only by the traditional invasive operative treatment. Thus, one of the goals of the modern dentistry is to find ways for non-invasive treatment of non-cavitated dental caries lesions in order to prevent the cavity formation. One of the main approaches to achieve this goal is through enhancing the remineralization process in order to restore the balance between the demineralization and the remineralization. Generally, the remineralization is defined as the process where calcium and phosphate ions are supplied from an external source to promote ion deposition into crystal defects in demineralized enamel. Nowadays, a range of novel calcium-phosphate-based delivery systems has been developed for clinical remineralization. Usually, these systems include either crystalline or amorphous (unstabilized or stabilized) calcium phosphates as well as fluoride-based formulations. Although the fluoride is beneficial for the enamel remineralization, the excessive intake of fluoride could induce dental fluorosis. Moreover, fluoride is known to adversely affect the tooth

development[7]. Therefore, the administration of fluoride-containing dental products should be carefully applied.

Recently, many biomimetic systems have been developed, including liquids and pastes, containing nano-apatite and/or different organic additives, for the remineralization of early, sub-micrometer-sized enamel lesions. Biomimetic reconstruction of tooth enamel is a topic of high relevance in dental material science as a novel approach for prevention, restoration, and treatment of defective enamel. In this respect, hydrogels containing chitosan and amelogenin were developed for enamel reconstruction, stabilizing Ca-P clusters and guiding their arrangement preferably into linear chains[8,9]. However, biomimetic strategies still face an ongoing challenge in the field of dental material science.

Beyond any doubt, the prophylactic methodologies for caries prevention could be more effective when combined with the antibacterial ideology. In this respect, it would be of great benefit to combine the remineralization systems with natural antimicrobials, e.g. chitosan. Chitosan is the deacetylated form of the natural polysaccharide – chitin. It is soluble under acidic conditions ($pK_b^{NH_2}=6.5$) and is an excellent antimicrobial[10,11]. Chitosan has been used for prevention of dental caries as it provides both bactericidal and/or bacteriostatic activities[12]. Chitosan is biocompatible and biodegradable. Below its pK_b , the amino groups of chitosan become protonated, which makes its macromolecules positively charged in acidic media. This overall positive charge makes chitosan adhesive to negatively charged surfaces such as tooth enamel, cell membranes, etc[10]. Recent studies have shown that chitosan had little effect on the remineralization process but it has anticariogenic activity because (i) it acts as a barrier against the acid penetration, contributing to the demineralization inhibition as well as (ii) it inhibits the release of phosphorus from the enamel thus interfering with the enamel demineralization[11].

Chitosan has been used as a structure forming agent in the formation of calcium phosphates, and the hybrid materials obtained in this way are widely applied for bone tissue regeneration and for dental mineral structures restorations[13,14]. So far, the following re-mineralizing agents based on chitosan and calcium phosphates were reported: carboxymethyl chitosan/amorphous calcium phosphate nanocomplexes[15], hybrid chitosan - HAP layers[16], chitosan/calcium pyrophosphate hybrid microflowers[17], etc. However, hybride materials based on chitosan micro- or nanogels and *in situ* deposited in them calcium phosphates have not been neither reported nor used for dental remineralization studies.

The aim of the present study is to reveal the potential of **hybrid chitosan/calcium phosphates microgels** for remineralization of *in vitro* demineralized enamel. These new materials combine the antimicrobial activity and bio-adherence of chitosan microgels with the remineralization ability of calcium phosphates. Furthermore, the hybrid microgels are expected not only to enhance the nucleation and growth processes on the demineralized enamel surface but also to act as a reservoir for calcium and phosphates ions thus strongly enhancing the remineralization process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Chitosan (MW 100 000 - 350 000) was purchased from Acros Organics, Belgium. Its degree of deacetylation was determined to be 79% using infrared spectroscopy method (data not shown). Calcium chloride, CaCl_2 (anhydrous), acetic acid and methacrylic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Potassium hydrogen phosphate, K_2HPO_4 (anhydrous) was purchased from Merck, Germany. Sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP) was synthesized according to procedure described elsewhere[18]. All reagents were used as received without further purification.

2.2. One-pot synthesis of chitosan microgels with *in situ* precipitated calcium phosphates

Chitosan (*Chi*) microgels (*MG*) were synthesized by ionotropic gelation. To this purpose, *Chi* (0.175 w/v%) was dissolved in 1 wt. % acetic acid by mild shaking and pH was adjusted to 4.76 with 10 N KOH. 10 ml 0.46M CaCl_2 were added to 50 ml from the *Chi* solution under continuous stirring. The TPP solution (0.291 w/v%) was prepared by dissolving TPP in 0.282M K_2HPO_4 . 10 ml from the TPP solution were added dropwise to the *Chi* solution under continuous stirring at 500 rpm. An opalescence of the final solution occurred due to the *in situ* formed calcium phosphates (*CaP*). Thus prepared samples were designated as *Chi_CaP MGs*.

As a referent sample, *Chi MG* without *CaP* were prepared using the same procedure as the described above but without CaCl_2 . In this way, neat chitosan microgels were obtained, further designated as *Chi_MG*.

2.3. Preparation of demineralized enamel lesions

Extracted human permanent molars and premolars without visible evidence of defects were obtained from the Dental Clinique, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Medical University of Sofia, Bulgaria. All patients were between 20- 65 years. All of them were informed and agreed with the

experimental study, providing written informed consents. After mechanical cleaning, teeth were immersed in 0.2% thymol storage solution at 4⁰C until being used according to the guidelines for handling of extracted teeth. The root and pulp of the teeth were removed and the coronary part was cut in bucco-lingual direction using diamond saw (Scheme 1A, see the arrow). In this way, two symmetric enamel slabs were obtained from each tooth.

The samples were carefully examined, selecting for the further remineralization studies only the intact and free of spots, cracks and other dental imperfections ones. The slabs were ultrasonically cleaned for 30 min and then rinsed with 75% ethanol.

In order to standardize the demineralized zones on the enamel surface, a window with size of 3x3 mm² (Scheme 1A) was outlined and the rest of the tooth surface was covered by water resistant nail varnish (Scheme 1B). The non-treated windows were the object of the further experimental studies, i.e. demineralization and remineralization.

Scheme 1. (A) Schematically presented area treated with methacrylic acid (designated with square); (B) line for symmetrical tooth sectioning; (C) two symmetrical slabs, subject of further demineralization and remineralization studies.

The two symmetrical samples obtained from each tooth were a subject of demineralization, creating in this way artificial demineralized lesions. Demineralization was performed at room temperature by using 1% gelatin gel prepared with 0.2 M aqueous solution of methacrylic acid. The slabs were immersed in 30 ml acidic gel, which was renewed every 24 h, for a total period of 4 days as described elsewhere[18,19]. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first one to apply methacrylic acid as a demineralizing agent. Methacrylic acid was selected because as an

organic acids, it is minimal invasive and closely mimics the chemical environment in the oral cavity[19]. The applied procedure for demineralization is a simple method for conducting reproducible experiments in a controllable and easy way.

After the demineralization, the samples were immersed in distilled water for 1 min, sonicated for 5 min and stored at 4⁰C in distilled water prior use.

Both symmetrical slabs coming from one tooth were used as follows: (i) the first slab was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and infrared spectroscopy in order to evaluate the demineralization degree and (ii) the second slab was a subject of remineralization. The effect of the remineralization was always evaluated by comparing both slabs from one tooth.

2.4. Remineralization of the demineralized enamel lesions with hybrid chitosan/calcium phosphates microgels

The demineralized tooth samples were carefully wiped to remove the excess water from their surfaces. Each tooth sample was immersed into freshly prepared *Chi_CaP* MGs suspension. After 6 hours, the samples were withdrawn from the remineralization media, rinsed with distilled water and left to dry at room conditions. Then the remineralization effect was followed by using several methods as described below for total remineralization time of 42 h (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Scheme of the remineralization process: enamel demineralized slabs were immersed in freshly prepared *Chi_CaP* MGs suspension for 6 hours, mimicking the night regime of the oral cavity. The procedure was repeated 7 times, i.e. the total remineralization time was 42 h.

In this demineralized enamel model study, the remineralization times were fixed to 6 hours, to correspond to the oral habits. Continuous remineralization in the oral cavity is restricted to the periods between dietary ingestion, i.e. between 1 and 4 h daytime or 6 to 8 h during the night. In this study, the remineralization during night periods was mimicked.

2.5. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) with Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX)

The morphology of the freeze dried powders from *Chi_CaP* MGs as well as from *Chi_MG* was studied by scanning electron microscope Lyra 3 XMU (Tescan), operating at 10kV coupled with EBSD and EDS analysis systems (Quantax 200, Bruker). Prior to the measurements, the samples were covered with a thin carbon film (~ 10 nm). The morphology of teeth before and after remineralization was examined by scanning electron microscope (JSM-5510, JEOL, Japan) operating at 10 kV. To prepare the samples for imaging, they were coated with gold for 30 s using a sputter-coater (JSC 1200, JEOL, Japan) under an inert argon atmosphere.

2.6. Transmission electron microscopy

The freeze dried powders from *Chi_CaP* MGs as well as from *Chi_MG* were studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). To this purpose, powder from each sample was suspended in water and dropped on a copper grid. The grids were placed and examined by TEM (JEOL-2100, 200 kV) with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX).

2.7. Attenuated Total Reflectance Infrared spectroscopy (ATR-IR)

The freeze dried powders from *Chi_CaP* MGs and *Chi_MG* as well as the teeth with artificial caries lesions and the remineralized ones were characterized by infrared spectroscopy (IR) in regime of attenuated total reflectance by using IRAffinity-1 Shimadzu Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrophotometer with MIRacle Attenuated Total Reflectance Attachment. The samples were studied as solids, without any preliminary treatment.

2.8. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and zeta potential measurements

DLS measurements were carried at 25°C using Zetasizer NanoBrook 90Plus Zeta (Brookhaven), equipped with a 35-mW red diode laser ($\lambda = 640$ nm) at a scattering angle of 90°. The ζ -potential was determined in a standard 1 cm cell via immersing BI SREL electrode.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of chitosan microgels with and without *in situ* formed calcium phosphates

3.1.1. Morphology of hybrid *Chi_CaP* MGs

The morphology of *Chi_CaP* MGs was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the obtained images are presented in Figure 1. The hybrid MGs are all spherical, but due to the *in situ* formed CaP in them some of the MGs have wall-deformed shape.

Figure 1. Morphology of chitosan microparticles with *in situ* formed calcium phosphates (*Chi_CaP*).

Both types of MGs – with and without CaP have hydrodynamic diameter above 100 nm as determined by SEM and DLS (Table S1), which is the reason that we designate them as *microgels*. The calcium phosphates deposition in *Chi_MG* results into an additional increase of the microgels stability as well as an additional crosslinking of the chitosan chains due to the *in situ* formed Ca-P particles (Table S1).

3.1.2. Composition of hybrid *Chi_CaP* MGs

The *in situ* formation of calcium phosphates in *Chi_CaP* MGs was demonstrated by SEM with EDX. For the hybrid *Chi_CaP* MGs, in addition to the detected for the neat chitosan microgels elements (**K** and **P**, Figure S2), also **Ca**, **Cl** and **P** were detected (Figure 2A). In Figures 2C and 2D, respectively, the distribution of **Ca** and **P** all over the studied sample could be seen. KCl is a by-product of CaP formation and that is why its presence in the sample will be not discussed.

(A)

(B)

Figure 2. SEM with EDX analysis of *Chi_CaP*: (A) elemental analysis; elemental maps of (B) both phosphorous and calcium; (C) only phosphorous, **P**, and (D) only calcium, **Ca**.

In Figure 2B, both elements, Ca and P, are presented together and the areas where they overlap forming CaP are seen in light blue due to the mixing of both colors (green for P and dark blue for Ca). Thus, the comparatively even distribution of *in situ* deposited calcium phosphates in the whole *Chi_CaP* MGs sample is clearly seen (Figure 2B).

3.1.3. ATR-IR study of chitosan hybride microgels

In order to characterize the *in situ* formed calcium phosphates into Chi MGs, ATR-IR spectra of both *Chi_MG* and *Chi_CaP* microgels were acquired. In general, CaP deposited in *Chi_MG* have the typical phosphate band in the 1000-1200 cm^{-1} region with two distinctive bands at $\sim 1074 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $\sim 1018 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which arise from the $\nu_3^{\text{PO}_4}$ stretching (Figure 3)[20].

Figure 3. ATR-IR spectra of *Chi_MG* and *Chi* MGs with *in situ* formed CaP (*Chi_CaP*).

The lower band indicates nonstoichiometric apatite containing HPO_2^- and CO_2 according a previously reported study of apatite minerals[21]. In agreement with this conclusion, Pleshko et al.[22] reported that the frequency at 1020 cm^{-1} has reduced wavenumber for less crystalline apatite minerals, e.g. it decreases from 1030 to 1015 cm^{-1} as the crystal size of the poorly crystalline HAP decreases from 19 to 12.5 nm .

Thus, it could be concluded that the hybride *Chi_CaP* microgels contain non-stechiometric poorly crystalline HAP. The conclusion is further supported by the shape of the band at $1000\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in Figure 3, which suggests that CaP are amorphous to poorly crystalline. For *well crystallized apatite*, the central contour in the region $1000\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is much narrower as compared to the contour of the poorly crystalline HAP[23]. Moreover, the high frequency shoulder in the same region is more clearly defined for crystalline HAP[23]. As the central contour is quite broad and the high frequency shoulder in the region $1000\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for *Chi_CaP* MGs is not well defined, this is another indication that the *in situ* formed CaP are rather poorly crystalline.

The bands at 862 cm^{-1} and 1456 cm^{-1} (Figure 3) are attributed to the CO_3^{2-} substitutes in the phosphate ion which typically occur in B-type hydroxyapatite[23]. It is more biologically

relevant than type A (where CO_3^{2-} group is substituting one OH group), as its amount in e.g. human skeleton is significantly higher compared to the type A[24,25]. Similar shift to 862 cm^{-1} of the band for the ν_2 stretching mode of CO_3^{2-} in carbonated HAP was observed when an ionic interaction between the HAP and alginate took place[26]. Thus, a possible ionic interaction between the chitosan and the carbonated HAP should be also considered here.

The IR spectrum of the neat chitosan microgels is discussed in details in the Supplementary Information.

3.1.4. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The fine structure of hybride chitosan/calcium phosphates microgels, *Chi_CaP* MGs, was characterized by TEM (Figure 4). In Figure 4A, an agglomerate formed by several *Chi_CaP* MGs is presented, each particle being with size $\sim 100\text{ nm}$ or below. The different density of the polymer (chitosan) and the inorganic particles (CaP) allows for better visualisation of the fine dispersion of the CaP into the chitosan MGs: the former are seen as dark points inside the chitosan light circles. The designated quadrate in Figure 4A (with a side $\sim 100\text{ nm}$) is further magnified in Figure 4B and 5C. In Figure 4C, the CaP particles size could be evaluated to be $\sim 2\text{-}3\text{ nm}$ and their fine dispersion in the chitosan microgels is clearly seen.

Figure 4. TEM of hybrid *Chi_CaP* MGs.

In Figure 5, a high resolution TEM picture of *Chi_CaP* MGs is presented where the CaP particles are more clearly seen. Some of these CaP particles are crystalline but others not (Figure 5), the crystalline CaP nanoparticles demonstrating a well ordered structure (Figure 5A) while the amorphous ones showing no order at all (Figure 5B).

Figure 5. TEM analysis of CaP nanoparticles formed *in situ* in *Chi_MGs*: (A) crystalline CaP nanoparticles and (B) amorphous CaP nanoparticles.

The TEM microscopy of *Chi_CaP* MGs (Figures 4 and 5) demonstrate that they are really hybrids as they consist of small CaP particles (~1-3 nm) finely dispersed within the Chi microgels matrix. The CaP particles are either amorphous or partially crystalline and the TEM study well coincides with the results from the X ATR-IR spectroscopy. Thus, the results from TEM analysis support the conclusions from the IR study, namely that the *in situ* formation of CaP in *Chi MGs* results into deposition of a mixture of (i) amorphous CaP and (ii) poorly crystalline carbonated HAp, type B, as revealed by the TEM and IR data.

The formation of a mixture of amorphous and poorly crystalline HAp is further supported by the X-ray characterization of the *Chi_CaP_MGs* (Figure S3, Supplementary Info). Besides the peaks for the by-product of the CaP deposition (sylvite, KCl), no peaks of HAp can be seen, meaning that the latter is X-ray amorphous. At a first sight, this is discrepancy between the results from the IR and the X-ray studies, as the former shows poorly crystalline CaP while the latter indicates amorphous CaP. However, both methods have different lower limits of detection of the

crystalline structure. The X-ray method is able to detect crystallites larger than ~ 5 nm[27], while IR spectroscopy could detect more poorly crystalline CaP[22]. Having in mind the size of the CaP particles detected by TEM (1-3 nm, Figure 5) this „discrepancy“ between both methods is easily understandable: the CaP nanoparticles size is too small to be registered by X ray.

3.2.Characterization of demineralized enamel lesions

3.2.1. SEM characterization of demineralized enamel lesions

The demineralized enamel slabs obtained through enamel treatment with methacrylic acid were studied by SEM (Figure 6).

Figure 6. SEM of demineralized enamel.

Fig. 6A reveals the heterogeneous morphology typical for intact enamel surface (before demineralization). The images B to F in Fig.6 show the demineralized defects. The SEM study proves that methacrylic acid effectively demineralized enamel and reveals details of its internal structure, such as inter-rods spaces and rods with their internal structure with c-axis oriented nano crystallites apatites. Moreover it is seen that edges of nano-crystallites are eroded as a result of the demineralization. In Figures 6B and 6C, the structure with preferential demineralisation of the *inter-rods zones* is clearly seen.

Thus, in this experimental study the performed demineralization of enamel by methacrylic acid show preferential dissolution of the inter rods, zones, and also revealed the internal rods-prismatic nano-crystalline hierarchical structure organization (Figures 6E and 6F). Thus, this study demonstrated that methacrylic acid is effective demineralizing agent for model enamel demineralization, as it clearly reveals the enamel nano-crystalline internal structure. Thus, it paves the way for a new nano-scale modelling of enamel demineralization. This phenomenon is not reported as far as we are aware, e.g. it is not observed when other organic acids as acrylic acid was applied for demineralization (our, non-presented studies). The mechanism of the methacrylic acid on demineralization deserves further investigations.

The results are supported by the IR spectra (Figure S4, Supplementary Information) which demonstrate that methacrylic acid successfully removes the upper aprismatic enamel layer revealing in this way the sub-layer of enamel rods and HAP crystallites. This sub-layer of the enamel consists of calcium phosphates which differ in their polymorphism, perfectness of the internal structures of enamel rods and inter prismatic zones, both of them built up by nano-crystalline apatite's.

3.3.Characterization of remineralized enamel lesions

3.3.1. ATR-IR study of the surface of remineralized enamel lesions

The ATR-IR spectra, by which the remineralization process of demineralized lesions was followed, are presented in Figure 7. During the first 18 h of remineralization (3 x 6 h), i.e. mimicking 3 nights' treatment of the enamel lesions with the *Chi_CaP* MGs remineralization suspension, the IR spectra do not change significantly. In the three spectra (Figure 7) the broad band between 900-1200cm⁻¹ appearing in the IR spectrum of the demineralized samples (Figure S4, Supplementary Information) does not change its shape and position. After the 4th day of the remineralization, however, this band starts to change – it splits into two bands, respectively at 989cm⁻¹ and 1052 cm⁻¹, designated in Figure 7 by arrows. These two bands can be assigned respectively to octacalcium phosphate (OCP, $\nu_1(\text{PO}_4^{3-})= 984 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and dicalcium phosphate dihydrate (DCPD, $\nu_3(\text{PO}_4^{3-})= 1055 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)[22].

Figure 7. ATR-IR spectra of demineralized enamel lesions after remineralization with *Chi_CaP* MGs suspension for different times.

The change that these two bands undergo during the 7-day period of remineralization is better illustrated in Table 1.

Thus, we could summarize that the remineralization procedure with *Chi_CaP* hybrid MGs needed an induction period (~ 3 days) during which period the amorphous and poorly crystalline calcium phosphates from the *Chi_CaP* hybrid MGs start to re-dissolve and respectively to deposit ions on the etched tooth surface. Thus, they act as a prenucleated CaP phase which enhances and supports the nucleation on the demineralized enamel lesions. After the 18h induction period, CaP start their secondary growth leading to the formation of a stable nano-scaled crystallites on the demineralized surface. As the remineralization time increases, the CaP start to form two new phases, as illustrated by the appearance of two new bands in the IR spectra (Figure 7, Table 1). These two bands can be assigned respectively to octacalcium phosphate (OCP, $\nu_1(\text{PO}_4^{3-}) = 984 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and dicalcium phosphate dihydrate (DCPD, $\nu_3(\text{PO}_4^{3-}) = 1055 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

¹)[23]. They become more and more distinctive and after the 6th day of remineralization they stop to change in their shape as well as in their position.

Table 1. Peak shifting and shape changes of 900-1200 cm⁻¹ characteristic band for remineralized tooth.

	$\nu_1(\text{PO}_4^{3-})_{\text{HAP}}$	$\nu_1(\text{PO}_4^{3-})_{\text{OCP}}$	$\nu_3(\text{PO}_4^{3-})_{\text{DCPD}}$	$\nu_3(\text{PO}_4^{3-})_{\text{HAP}}$	$\nu_1(\text{PO}_4^{3-})_{\text{OCP}}$	$\nu_1(\text{PO}_4^{3-})_{\text{OCP}}$
0d	960 cm ⁻¹	1014 cm ⁻¹		1084 cm ⁻¹	Does not appear	Does not appear
1d	No change	No change		No change	Does not appear	Does not appear
2d	No change	No change		No change	Does not appear	Does not appear
3d	No change	No change		No change	Does not appear	Does not appear
4d	Starts to disappear	Splits into two bands at:		Disappears	1119 cm ⁻¹	1134 cm ⁻¹
		989 cm ⁻¹	1053 cm ⁻¹	Disappears		
5d	Starts to disappear	986 cm ⁻¹	1053 cm ⁻¹	Disappears	1119 cm ⁻¹	1134 cm ⁻¹
6d	Starts to disappear	986 cm ⁻¹	1053 cm ⁻¹	Disappears	1119 cm ⁻¹	1134 cm ⁻¹
7d	Fully disappears	986 cm ⁻¹	1053 cm ⁻¹	Disappears	1119 cm ⁻¹	1136 cm ⁻¹

The final result from the remineralization with *Chi_CaP* MGs is quite encouraging in terms of the deposited CaP on the demineralized enamel surface. It is well known that both OCP and DCPD are the main precursors for HAP formation in biological tissues[28,29]. So, the developed in the present study remineralization procedure is in fact a biologically relevant process of remineralization on the demineralized enamel surface and it passes through the stages characteristic for the natural HAP formation process.

3.3.2. SEM study of remineralized enamel lesions

The morphology of the enamel surfaces after remineralization with *Chi_CaP* MGs demonstrates noticeable transformation in the nanostructure of enamel rods (Figure 8). After 7 days of remineralization, the nanocrystalline enamel structure (prism and inter-prismatic zones) is upgraded by grain-like newly formed materials (~ 50 nm) and these newly formed structures are most probably a result from the non-classical crystallisation processes (Figures 8 B, C, D)[30]. At the end of the remineralization procedure, the whole acid-demineralized enamel lesions are covered by enamel-like structures as it is seen in Fig. 8A-D.

Figure 8. SEM images after the remineralization of demineralized enamel lesions (A, B). Details of new nano crystalline structures formed on the top of native enamel nano-crystallites (C, D).

It should be reminded here, that another important factor for the successful re-mineralization process is the enamel itself. The enamel is not only a substrate that hosts the newly formed nano-structures (Fig.8 C,D) but it could also act as a functional template for nucleation and crystal growth. In this respect, the revealed after demineralization nano-crystallites in internal prismatic enamel structure (Figure 6D-F) could act as active nucleation sites for the successful remineralization process of the enamel slabs in the light of the non-classical crystallization[30].

4. Conclusions

In the present study we have developed for the first time hybrid chitosan/calcium phosphates microgels and demonstrated that they are effective agents for enhancing the nucleation and growth of calcium phosphates on the model demineralized enamel surface. During the hybrid

microgels formation, chitosan macromolecules act as a template for the CaP deposition and thus amorphous to poorly crystalline non stoichiometric HAP was *in situ* formed.

The obtained *Chi_CaP* MGs have several advantages as remineralization agents, namely: (i) as the chitosan is bio-adhesive, it ensures better adhesion between the *Chi_CaP* MGs and the demineralized enamel; (ii) they serve as a “reservoir” for calcium and phosphates ions and in this way supply the demineralized enamel with adequate amount of ions, necessary for its biomimetic mineralization; (iii) they possess also antimicrobial properties as the chitosan is well known and proved to be an effective natural antimicrobial agent.

Moreover, the applied for the first time as a model demineralization agent methacrylic acid is demonstrated to reveal the fine structure of the enamel prisms. Thus, the obtained internal enamel nano-structure could act as a nucleating template for effective mineralization. The developed in the present study remineralization procedure could be further applied for caries prevention as it relies on non-toxic components. Thus, the study reveals a simple approach for remineralization of initial enamel demineralization.

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